

The Effects of 21st Century Social Media Influencers on Student's Academic Performance

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Abstract

In the twenty-first century, students are capable of navigating the online platforms. Hence, the purpose of this study was to determine the impact of media influencers on student academic performance. The study aligns with gathering the demographic profile of the participants and identifying social media influencers based on entertainment and educational content at Kalangyawon National High School during the school year 2023-2024 as the basis for the recommendation plan. A survey questionnaire was used to conduct the quantitative descriptive analysis. The 4-Likert scale was used by the sixty (60) participants to evaluate the variables of the study. The study utilizes the frequency and percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson R. The findings suggest that participants mostly followed the entertainment content with a mean of 3.08 or agree while educational influencers they followed to motivate them to study well with a mean of 3.08 or agree. Furthermore, it reveals that only Grade 9 participants have reached 84.70, or a satisfactory level while others explicitly revealed that they have reached a very satisfactory level towards their academic performance. Based on the result of this study, the recommendation plan is to conduct a short orientation and encourage learners to follow more educational influencers and engage them in school events.

Keywords: Social Media Influencers, KNHS students, Academic Performance, Carcar City

Introduction

In the 21st century, the rise of social media platforms has given birth to a new phenomenon: social media influencers. These sensation of being a social media influencers build themselves as content creators and experts in varied fields while sharing their knowledges and experiences to the online platforms. Influencers create and share content regularly to establish their expertise and work to build a relationships with their followers. According to Freberg, K., et al. (2010), social media influencers who develop their social capital serve as important advocates who have the power to sway public opinion. The term "social media influencers" (SMIS) refers to a wide range of people who have gained on social media, suggesting that the following of these content creators go far beyond their networks (Booth, N., & Matic, J.A., 2011). The advent and widespread use of social media platforms have revolutionized the way individuals communicate, and co some information (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

According to a study of Garcia, PRJM., et al. (2018), social media influencers have become an integral part of the daily lives of millions of people worldwide, especially among the younger generations since these personalities are always available in the online community such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Tiktok and others in which brought significant opinion, choices, and behaviors of the audience (Taylor, 2021). This influence extends to various aspects of life, including education. The growth of social media was also accompanied by the proliferation of social media influencers. A Pew Research study in 2015 proved that there had been an increase in the number of people who turned to Facebook and Twitter for news updates between the years 2013 and 2015 (Barthel, R., et al. 2015). The creation and sustenance of their social media influence were greatly pinned on the maintenance of close relationships with their pools of followers. Within the early and mid-2010s, influencers became popular for their online content and channels on social media (Ahmad, S.R., 2017).

These social media influencers are reputed to have expertise in an area about which they create content and share this content with followers on social media (Geysler, W., 2022). The purpose of this research is to explore the effects of 21st-century social media influencers on student's academic performance at Kalangyawon National High School. By conducting a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, surveys, and interviews. This study aims to provide a deeper understanding of the various in which social media influencers may influence students' academic performance.

Literature Review

Moore, S., et. al. (2018) stated that social media influencers have many followers who trust them, especially on topics related to their domain of knowledge.

Hudders L., et. al. (2021), assert that impact and reach are essential traits of social media influencers. Impact indicates an influencer’s ability to affect their audience’s decision-making, whereas reach relates to the influencer’s primary and secondary relationships with followers. Larger audiences are drawn to influencers because of their intimacy, authenticity, and level of skill.

Pligt, J. & Vliek, M., (2016) stated that according to the Psychology Influence perspective, people, often, do not realize that they are influenced because the effect occurs mainly in their subconscious.

According to Leon Festinger's theory, people assess themselves by contrasting their skills, beliefs, and characteristics with those of others. Influencers on social media frequently present an unrealistic picture of accomplishment and success. Pupils may attempt to attain comparable academic standards by comparing themselves to role models, which can harm their motivation, self-worth, and ultimately their academic achievements.

Chang, A. J., et al. (2020) stated that social media influencers with significant numbers of subscribers and passionate followers on social media, and with the ability to influence their thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors.

Brown, D., & Hayes, N., (2008) stated that social media influencers (SMIs) are individual users or entities on social media who have established authority and credibility among potential customers in a specific industry through their online activities.

Karima L., (2023) stated that 70 percent of the teenagers believe that they trust social media influencers more than traditional celebrities, indicating the huge impact of these people have on minors. However, influencers can also have a positive effect on their followers. For certain individuals, it transcends beyond a career and is regarded as a way of life. Every day, influencers utilize social media to share their thoughts and criticisms on a wide range of subjects and products, including lifestyle, health, and beauty.

Sokolova, K., et al., (2020) noted that social media influencers are seen as reliable and reputable information providers.

Kunkel, D. et al. (2004) believed that youths' identity formation is influenced by social media influencers.

Han, E, & Ryu, E. (2021) defined an influencer as a person with millions or hundreds of thousands of followers on social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. Influencers can generate and engage with a vast amount of multimedia content, share their lives with customers, and respond to reviews and comments on online social networks.

Methodology

This study evaluated how student's academic performance was impacted by social media influencers of the twenty-first century. Initially, we administered a survey questionnaire to a sample of ten randomly selected students from Kalangyawon National High School's classes 7–12. The process, input, and output represent the three stages of the research flow in this study. The study's input includes the demographic profile of the participants, including age, gender, and grade level; who the social media influencers are for both educational and entertaining content; and the participants' overall academic performance as well as their study habits and general average. Thus study shows the survey questionnaire and the method which is the quantitative-correlational method. The final output shows the recommendation plan of this study.

Results and Discussion

The 21st social media influencers have been continuing the process of influencing students on their academic performance, especially on how they study in school, particularly on their general average and study habits. Table 4 shows the results on how social media influencers affect students in different ways. One of these greater influences is they agreed on all the characteristics of social media influencers including the entertainment content that affects their mental health. On their general average where they feel that educational influencers have encouraged them to improve their general average. All of these show that they all agreed to the following indicators that they have answered the survey questionnaire.

Table 1
Age of the Participants

Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
11-12	7	11.67
13-14	18	30.00
15-16	21	35.00
17-18	9	15.00
19-20	5	8.33

This table shows the ages of the participants who answered the survey questionnaire. Based on the table, we have found out that most teenagers from 15-16 years old are following social media influencers in their school especially in Kalangyawon National High School, for about thirty-five

percent (35%). A 2022 survey found that 35% of teens aged 13 to 17 use at least one of five social media platforms more than several times a day. These platforms include YouTube, TikTok, Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat. This frequent usage increases their exposure to influencers (Zara Abrams, 2023).

Table 2
Gender of the Participants

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Female	36	60.00
Male	24	40.00

Based on the table, most females are more likely to follow social media influencers than males. Previous studies have found different patterns in online activities between men and women (Boneva, R.S., et al., 2001). Females were likely to spend more time visiting websites, sending/receiving emails, and on instant messaging than males, whereas males were more likely than females to invest time in computer gaming (Park, N. & Lee, KM., 2014).

Table 3
Grade level of the Participants

Grade level	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
7	10	16.67
8	10	16.67
9	10	16.67
10	10	16.67
11	10	16.67
12	10	16.67
Total	60	100

In the table shown, all grade levels are willing to participate in administration of the test. We choose randomly by grade level but limited in only ten (10) participants and we found out that all of them answered the survey questionnaire. A study published in the Journal of Social Psychology, the study revealed that students in higher grade levels tend to follow influencers more actively and are more likely to be influenced by their content (Journal of Social Psychology).

Table 4
Social Media Influencers on Students

	Frequency (f)	Categorical Responses
Characteristics of social media influencers on students	2.81	Agree
The influence of social media influencers on student's general average	2.90	Agree
The influence of social media influencers on student's study habits	2.75	Agree

This table is classified into the following: the characteristics of social media influencers; the influence of social media influencers on student's general average, and the influence of social media influencers on student's study habits. Social media influencers are being identified by their characteristics. With the frequency of 2.81 "agree".

Influencers are people who have great power of influence in social networks, with many followers and with great significance among children, adolescents, and young people (García, et al, 2018). The social media influencers have a different impact on students' general average, with a frequency of 2.90 or "agree". This engagement can affect the influencers' overall performance, including their general average (Abdullah Al-Ansi, et al., 2023).

These social media influencers are continuously affecting the students, especially their performance in school. Students neglect their studies by spending time on social networking websites rather than studying or interacting with people in person. This statement revealed the frequency of 2.75 or "agree". They forgot the task that will be assigned to them. Actively and frequently participating in social networking can negatively affect their grades or hamper their journey to their future careers (Wilbert Villafior, et al 2017).

Table 5
 Correlation

Correlations

		Characteristics	AcademicPerformance
Characteristics	Pearson Correlation	1	.340**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008
	N	60	60
AcademicPerformance	Pearson Correlation	.340**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 shows the correlational analysis of the characteristics of social media influencers on student's academic performance. This correlation uses the Pearson R correlational method. From the characteristics of social media influencers on students, the Pearson Correlation is equivalent to 1, while from the academic performance is equivalent to .340. Its significance is 2-tailed and the academic performance is .008 and the total participant of this study is sixty (60) who answered the survey questionnaire. Therefore, the correlation between the characteristics of social media influencers on students and their academic performance is highly significant at the level of 0.01 or 2-tailed.

Table 6

Correlations

		Influence	AcademicPerformance
Influence	Pearson Correlation	1	.308*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.017
	N	60	60
AcademicPerformance	Pearson Correlation	.308*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	
	N	60	60

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 shows the Correlation analysis of the influence of social media influencers on the student's general average and their academic performance. Moreover, this correlation is used by the Pearson R method. From the influence of social media influencers on their general average, the Pearson Correlation is equivalent to 1, while from their academic performance, it is equivalent to .308. Its significance is 2-tailed and the academic performance is .017, and the total population of this study is sixty (60) who answered the survey questionnaire. Therefore, the correlation between the influence of social media influencers on their general average and academic performance is highly significant at the level of 0.05 or 2-tailed.

Table 7

Correlations

		StudyHabits	AcademicPerformance
StudyHabits	Pearson Correlation	1	.149
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.254
	N	60	60
AcademicPerformance	Pearson Correlation	.149	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.254	
	N	60	60

Table 7 shows the correlation analyses of the influence of social media influencers on student's study habits and their academic performance. Moreover, this correlation uses the Pearson R correlational method. This reveals that the influence of social media influencers on their study habits, the Pearson Correlation is equivalent to 1, while the academic performance is equivalent to .149. From its significance is 2-tailed, the academic performance is equivalent to .254, and the total participant of this study is sixty (60). Therefore, the correlation between the influence of social media influencers and academic performance is also significant to each other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study aimed to explore the effects of 21st-century social media influencers on students' academic performance using a quantitative correlational method through a survey questionnaire. The research delved into the demographic profiles of participants and assessed the impact of social media influencers on academic performance, considering both entertainment and educational content. The findings revealed that a significant number of students, particularly those aged 15–16, follow social media influencers, primarily for entertainment purposes. Interestingly, students expressed agreement that educational influencers motivate them to work harder and improve their general average. However, there was a consensus that spending more time on social media influencers could potentially lower overall academic performance.

Additionally, the study highlighted that the content posted by social media influencers significantly impacts students' study habits, with a majority agreeing to this influence. Despite mixed responses regarding the positive motivation from influencers to develop effective study habits, social media influencers play a role in shaping students' approaches to studying. The research emphasizes the influence of social media influencers on students, affecting both entertainment preferences and educational engagement. It is crucial to recognize these impacts to formulate targeted recommendations for addressing potential challenges and fostering positive influences on academic performance and study habits.

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